

Rac-5a

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3a-rac-30%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	36	Acq. Method Set:	30%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 3a rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/9/2022 8:04:48 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/20/2022 11:19:43 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.395	4814708	50.03	320735
2	10.201	4809608	49.97	250259

Asy-5a

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3a-asy-30%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	73	Acq. Method Set:	30%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3A ASY
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/9/2022 11:29:43 AM CST		
Date Processed:	10/20/2022 11:18:24 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.357	16304381	96.04	1094434
2	10.137	672650	3.96	35667